

Gimnastika darsining maqsadlari, vositalari va uslubiy xususiyatlari

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Anatatsiya: *Jismoniy tarbiyada umumiy jismoniy rivojlanish va insonning asosiy motor qobiliyatlarini yaxshilashni ta'minlaydigan gimnastika alohida o'rin tutadi. Gimnastika turli xil mashqlar bilan ajralib turadi, bu aniqlarni eng muvaffaqiyatli hal qilish uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratadi*

Kalit so'zlar: *Gimnastika, sog'lomlashtirish, saf mashqlari, sakrash, erkin mashq, akrobatika, xoreografiya.*

Gimnastikaning har xil turlari bilan shug'ullanish qaror qabul qilishga yordam beradi eng muhim vazifalardan biri jismoniy tayyorgarlikni ta'minlashdir jismoniy va ma'naviy kuchlarning uyg'un rivojlanishi bilan kuchli yosh avlod.

Gimnastika-maxsus tanlangan jismoniy tizim salomatlikni mustahkamlash, uyg'un jismoniy tarbiya va insonning motor qobiliyatini, uning kuchini, epchilligini, tezligini, chidamliligini, moslashuvchanligini yaxshilash uchun ishlatiladigan mashqlar, uslubiy texnikalar.

Gimnastika vazifalari

1) sog'lomlashtirish-salomatlikni mustahkamlash, individual mushak guruhlarini va butun mushak tizimini rivojlantirish; individual organlarda funktsional anormalliklarni bartaraf etish va oldini olish

va tana tizimlari; to'g'ri holatni, yurishni shakllantirish; nafas olish va yurak-qon tomir tizimining umumiy rivojlanishi va mustahkamlanishi, metabolizmni yaxshilash va tananing ish faoliyatini yaxshilash;

2) ta'lim-hayotiy vosita ko'nikmalarini, ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish (shu jumladan amaliy va sport) va har tomonlama jismoniy rivojlanish, kuch, moslashuvchanlik, muvofiqlashtirish va harakatlarning ekspressivligini tarbiyalashga yordam beradigan maxsus bilimlar bilan qurollanish;

3) tarbiyaviy-axloqiy va irodaviy fazilatlarni tarbiyalash, intizom, kollektivizm, jasorat, qat'iyatlilik, qat'iyatlilik, qat'iyatlilik, chidamlilik, tashabbuskorlik va boshqalar. Gimnastikada estetik fazilatlarni – harakat madaniyatini, musiqiy fazilatlarni tarbiyalashda katta o'rin egallaydi ta'mi, ritm hissi.

Gimnastika vositalari

1) saf mashqlari-safdagi qo'shma harakatlar (shu jumladan yakka). Ular tashkilotchilik va intizomni tarbiyalashga yordam beradi, birgalikda uyushgan

harakatlarga o'rgatadi, insonning to'g'ri holatini shakllantiradi, qiladi u yanada ohangdor, ingichka. Burg'ulash mashqlari katta pedagogik ahamiyatga ega, chunki ular tufayli o'qituvchi talabalarni to'g'ri tashkil etish imkoniyatiga ega, birgalikda harakat qilish uchun ularni zalga yoki saytga joylashtirish, shuningdek vosita muammolarini hal qilish tavsiya etiladi darsda;

2) umumiy rivojlanish mashqlari (URM) mushak-skelet tizimini va butun tanani yaxshilashga yordam beradi

umuman olganda, ular to'g'ri holatni shakllantiradi. Ular umumiy maqsadga qaratilgan jismoniy rivojlanish va talabalarni o'zlashtirishga tayyorlash keyinchalik murakkab motorli harakatlar. Ushbu guruhga quyidagilar kiradi kuch, moslashuvchanlikni rivojlantirish uchun turli xil mashqlar, tezlik, muvofiqlashtirish, mushaklarni kuchaytirish va bo'shashtirish qobiliyati. Umumiy rivojlanish mashqlari, vazifalarga qarab, ob'ektlarsiz va turli xil narsalar (to'plar, arqonlar, gimnastika tayoqchalari, dumbbelllar, rezina) bilan bajarilishi mumkin amortizatorlar va boshqalar). Xuddi shu guruhga mashqlar kiradi sherikning qarshiligi bilan juftlikda. URM tasniflanadi anatomik asosda:

- a) bo'yin, qo'l va elkama-kamar uchun mashqlar;
- b) magistral uchun;
- c) oyoqlar uchun;
- d) butun tana uchun.

URM tuzatish, gigiena, ishlab chiqarish, asosiy, sport mashg'ulotlarining asosiy mazmunini tashkil etadi va sport va amaliy gimnastika;

3) amaliy mashqlar – yugurish, yurish, uloqtirish, to'qqa chiqish, to'siqlarni engib o'tish. Ularning yordami bilan talabalar asosiy hayotiy ko'nikma va ko'nikmalarni egallaydilar, ularni turli xil sharoitlarda qo'llashni o'rganing. Amaliy mashqlar yordamida harakatlarning umumiy muvofiqlashtirilishi yaxshilanadi, individual mushak guruhlari rivojlanadi va mustahkamlanadi. Kompleksda qo'llaniladigan amaliy mashqlar ko'p qirrali jismoniy rivojlanishning samarali vositalaridan biridir;

4) sakrash-bu o'quvchilarning muvofiqlashtirish qobiliyatini yaxshilashning yaxshi vositasi. Ular yurak-qon tomir va nafas olish tizimlariga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi, shuning uchun ular gimnastikada muhim o'rin tutadi;

5) gimnastika jihozlaridagi mashqlar gimnastikaning asosiy mazmunini tashkil qiladi. Bu barlarda, halqalarda, parallel barlarda, otda, logda, turli balandlikdagi barlarda mashqlar-sportning eng xarakterli vositalari gimnastika. Ularning asosiy maqsadi harakatlarni muvofiqlashtirishni yaxshilashdir. Ushbu gimnastika jihozlarida mashqlarni muvaffaqiyatli o'zlashtirish uchun har tomonlama jismoniy tayyorgarlik, shuningdek kuch, moslashuvchanlik, vestibulyar apparatlar va ixtiyoriy fazilatlarining yuqori darajadagi rivojlanishi majburiydir. Chig'anoqlarning dizayn xususiyatlari va g'ayrioddiy

qo'llab-quvvatlash shartlari (asosan qo'llarda) ushbu mashqlarning sezilarli intensivligini belgilaydi.

Ushbu snaryadlardan tashqari, gimnastikada ommaviy turdagi snaryadlar keng qo'llaniladi (bir vaqtning o'zida frontal, oqim va boshqa usullar bilan mashq qilish uchun). Bularga gimnastika devorlari va skameykalar, arqonlar, zinapoyalar, shuningdek, bir vaqtning o'zida turli xil mashqlarni katta guruhlarda bajarishga imkon beradigan ko'p to'plamli snaryadlar kiradi;

6) erkin mashqlar – akrobatika va xoreografiya elementlari bilan birgalikda turli xil gimnastika mashqlarining kombinatsiyasi. Bunday kombinatsiyalar sport tasnifida belgilangan talablarga muvofiq tuziladi. Asosiy kompozitsiyaning maqsadi muvofiqlashtirish qobiliyatlarini takomillashtirish, harakatlarning ritmi va go'zalligini tarbiyalashdir. Erkin mashqlar maktabni shakllantirishning samarali vositasidir harakatlar. Ular ob'ektlarsiz (sportda) bajarilishi mumkin

gimnastika) va turli xil mavzular bilan (badiiy gimnastikada, ommaviy gimnastika chiqishlarida);

7) akrobatik mashqlar keng doiraga ega qiyinchiliklar oddiydan eng murakkabgacha. Muvofiqlashtirish va mushaklarning harakatlari uchun oddiy mashqlar dasturga kiritilgan birinchi kurs gimnastikachilarini tayyorlash. Barcha jismoniy rivojlanishning juda yuqori darajasini talab qiladigan murakkab mashqlar inson qobiliyatlari, faqat yuqori malakali sportchilar uchun mavjud. Akrobatik mashqlar muhim ahamiyatga ega jismoniy va axloqiy irodani takomillashtirish vositasi sifatlar, kuch, tezlik, epchillik, jasorat, qat'iyatlilik va boshqalar. Ular kosmosda yo'nalishni turli yo'llar bilan tarbiyalaydilar va vestibulyar apparatni mashq qilishda muhim vosita hisoblanadi.

8) badiiy va ritmik gimnastika mashqlari turli xil harakatlarni o'z ichiga oladi, shu jumladan va raqs. Ular musiqiy akkompaniment bilan uzviy bog'liqdir va tinglovchilarning estetik tarbiyasiga hissa qo'shadi. Ushbu mashqlar ayollar bilan mashg'ulotlarda qo'llaniladi.

Gimnastika darslarida turli xil turlari keng qo'llaniladi ko'plab muhim ko'nikmalarni, ko'nikmalarni takomillashtirish va mustahkamlash, shuningdek, ishtirokchilarning hissiy ohangini oshirish uchun ochiq o'yinlar va sport estafetalari.

Gimnastikaning yuqoridagi asosiy vositalarini, ularning asosiy ta'sirini hisobga olgan holda, birlashtirish tavsiya etiladi

quyidagicha:

a) jismoniy rivojlanishning umumiy rivojlanishiga qaratilgan mashqlar fazilatlar va vosita qobiliyatlari (bular burg'ulash mashqlari, URM, ochiq o'yinlar va estafetalar);

b) hayotiy vosita qobiliyatlari va ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish (amaliy mashqlar, sakrash);

v) motor qobiliyatlari va ixtiyoriy fazilatlarni jadal rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish (erkin mashqlar, qo'llab-quvvatlash sakrashlari, gimnastika jihozlarida mashqlar, akrobatik mashqlar va badiiy gimnastika mashqlari).

Asosiy gimnastika mashqlarining bunday bo'linishi ularni muayyan pedagogik muammolarni hal qilish uchun tanlashni osonlashtiradi.

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